

OUTLINE OF DOCTORAL RESEARCH TO BE COMPLETED IN DECEMBER 1971

My research project for submission to the Department of Oriental Studies in supplication for the degree of D. Phil. is entitled:
"Archaeological and documentary material for the history and mechanisms of commerce in Southern Iran from the seventh century to the end of the Portuguese Period."

The commercial importance of Southern Iran in historical times until the development of the route to the East around the Cape of Good Hope is well documented. A succession of major port cities which flourished on the barren North shore of the Persian Gulf were renowned throughout the world for their commercial wealth. However, the reasons for their location, their size, and for the rise and decline of each in succession have not as yet been adequately explained. For the period under study the area provides an unique opportunity for studying the mechanisms of mediaeval commerce. There is a large amount of documentary material from divergent sources, Arab and Persian official and semi-official accounts, the reports of Chinese, Islamic, and European travellers, and Portuguese state papers, to name the most important. These sources, written from very different points of view often incidentally provide valuable material on the changing trade and commercial life of the area. They supply essential evidence on the perishable commodities of trade, on important towns, and on the routes taken between them. However, these sources are frequently contradictory and never touch on a quantitative assessment of the size of sites, or more than hint at the relative importance of different commodities, routes, or trading areas.

Archaeological fieldwork then was undertaken to test the relative validity of varying historical accounts and to provide as much quantitative data as possible on the size of settlements and of the trade between them. This fieldwork has consisted of a non-intensive archaeological survey of much of Southern Iran and an intensive survey of the Persian Gulf coast and islands from Jask to Bushehr. Survey in the coastal area has proved particularly valuable, first because the excavations at Siraf provide a stratigraphic date for almost every type of pottery found, second because of the great mobility of settlement in the past (discussed in greater detail in my Research Project), and finally because of the considerable commercial activity in the area, as revealed in the excavations at Siraf.

The ceramic, glass, and other archaeological materials which are collected in this survey can now be dated fairly closely by reference to the artefacts recovered from the stratigraphic excavations at Siraf, supplemented by my own excavations at Sirjan and Kacht-i Beh. Special attention has been paid to identifying the place of manufacture of distinctive types of pottery and glass. The excavations on the kilns at Siraf have clearly demonstrated that characteristic pottery types were produced on this site. In addition, over the last three years eleven separate kiln sites have been located on the surface in different areas. The excavations at Sirjan in 1970 examined a production area located during surface survey, and conclusively identified the large range of fine pottery produced there. The distribution from all these kilns gives an illuminating picture of the local trade in ceramics. The direction of long distance trade is demonstrated in the distribution of pottery, glass, and porcelains identified as originating in Mesopotamia,

the Persian Plateau, the Levant, or the Far East. Further useful material has emerged on trade in building stone. An attempt is also being made to identify the sources of the steatite found in abundance on many sites. Through mapping the distribution of oyster middens and by examining intermingled or associated pottery and glass, the location and extent of the pearling industry is being illustrated at different periods.

By carefully recording the rounded and unrounded size of every site, it has proved possible to provide, for the intensively surveyed coastal area, a valid impression of the distribution and concentration of settlement in each of eight ceramic periods. An attempt is being made to relate these figures on the size of sites to very approximate figures on population size. To this end population densities are being obtained for modern villages and towns of different habitation types. These will be compared against figures for the 16th to 17th century city of New Bombay, which are being obtained by relating contemporary population figures, descriptions, and drawings to the present ruin field.

Using archaeological methods it has, of course, been impossible to examine trade in other than imperishable objects, such as glass, pottery, and stone. There is, however, no reason to suppose that this trade was unrepresentative of the general movement of people and goods, especially since these imperishable materials were used as containers for more perishable goods. From the thousands of sherds of Chinese storage jars found on the Persian Gulf coast, only one bears a stamped and readable, but unfortunately incomplete, inscription. Its three characters read "pure

spirit (essence) of ...", and would, I am assured, be a normal formula for the description of spice or pharmaceutical products which the jar was undoubtedly designed to hold. Certainly in Southern Iran today trade in pottery and glass is dependent on the existence of prior lines of communication developed for the distribution of other commodities.

The archaeological evidence for Islamic commerce in Southern Iran has proved most suggestive. Among other results, the maps illustrating the quantitative distribution of pottery types have provided useful material on the relative importance of land and sea routes from West to East and on the trading spheres of different ports inland, on the Persian coast, and as far away as East Africa.

In investigating the historically attested trade routes, it has been found that on the Iranian plateau virtually no pottery or glass was traded along the route from Shiraz to Bam through Sirjan which figures so prominently in the Islamic geographers' accounts of the overland route to Seistan and the Indus. These three cities are contained in separate, scarcely overlapping areas within which fine pottery was distributed from kilns situated near Istakhr, at Sirjan, and at an unknown site near Bam or in Persian Seistan. On the coast, however, large quantities of pottery were traded long distances. Even items of such low value as the domestic coarse ware from the Siref kilns were traded to Minab, five hundred kilometres down the coast, while storage jars reached as far as East Africa. However, very little of this pottery was traded inland across the Zagros, for example, glazed pottery from Mesopotamia, which was traded in large quantities

throughout the Persian Gulf and adjacent areas in mediaeval times, is very rare on the Iranian Plateau. Similarly, from the coming of Islam Far Eastern pottery and porcelain are found in large quantities in the warm lands around the Persian Gulf. However, until the 14th century A.D. very little penetrated further inland. The city sites of Sirjan, Kirman, and Istakhr are the only mounds on the southern plateau with Far Eastern pottery antedating the 14th century A.D.. Instead, the Chinese ceramics found in such quantities at Siraf and Kish were shipped to Mesopotamia. From the 14th century A.D. there is a significant change in the pattern, and forty-two sites on the southern plateau have been recorded with 14th to 16th century A.D. celadon or blue and white. By this period it seems that the economic hinterland of the major Persian ports was shifting from Mesopotamia and the West to the Iranian Plateau.

It has proved possible also to provide information on the trading spheres of the different cities of the Gulf at different periods. For example, in the 9th to 10th century A.D. pottery of types made at or near Siraf is found distributed all over the Persian Gulf, and is a standard import in East African sites like Kilwa. However, in the 12th to 13th century A.D. levels at Kilwa there is no imported pottery characteristic of contemporary Siraf. Instead, nearly all imported pottery is similar to types found at Old Hormuz, and some sherds were almost certainly made in the kilns there. The distribution in the Gulf from these kilns, unlike the wide distribution from the Siraf kilns, was limited to an area of about one hundred and fifty kilometres from Old Hormuz. This presumably reflects the political and commercial division of the lower Gulf between the rulers

of Hormuz and Kish which is recorded in documentary sources. Thus, in the absence of documentary material, we can conclude from the distribution of pottery that first the Siraf merchants and then merchants from Hormuz, rather than those from Kish, dominated the Gulf's East African trade.

The study of site distribution by period has revealed remarkable chronological changes. Several documentary sources refer to the abandonment at different periods of towns like Siraf and Kish, and mention the migration of groups and individuals to the commercial centres which replaced them. The archaeological evidence not only confirms these accounts, but also reveals migration as a process apparently involving whole regions. For example, for thirty kilometres on either side of Siraf the area of sites in the 12th to 13th centuries A.D. is less than fifteen per cent that of the 9th to 10th centuries A.D., the period when Siraf was thriving. There is no documentary material about Bushahr in the very early Islamic Period, since we lack detailed sources before the late 8th century, but a similar decline in the area of sites in the Bushahr Peninsula occurred before the 9th to 10th century A.D., and suggests that the immediate predecessor of Siraf is one of several large sites near Bushahr. Certainly this great mobility of settlement seems to indicate how much the inhabitants of the Gulf were dependent for their livelihood on changing political and commercial situations in the Gulf itself, rather than on agriculture or trade inland along specific routes. Significant perhaps of the level of commercial activity is that settlement in the Early Islamic Period seems to have been larger in area and more concentrated than at any later period. Although over eighty sites have material predating Islam, it has not proved possible in this study to investigate the earlier period in which Gulf trade grew to such great proportions.

As outlined in my Research Project, important discoveries were made of remains connected with pearling. Special emphasis is placed on these finds, which are particularly common in the Early Islamic Period, since pearling might have played a central role in attracting world trade to the lower Gulf. Documentary sources stress the part played by the great lower Gulf ports in transmitting Oriental products to Mesopotamia and the West. This has traditionally been regarded simply as a transit trade, but such a view hardly explains why, for at least one thousand years, the great trading centres of the Persian Gulf were on the lower Gulf rather than on the edge of Mesopotamia. Furthermore, Mesopotamia and the West offered no commodities, except Mesopotamian glass, which were definitely traded to the East, while a great deal of modern research has established that for some reason the spice trade did not result in the vast drain of precious metals that Roman and mediæval writers feared. Clearly the West obtained its pearls through an intermediary which was of more than transit importance and played a real role in generating the spice trade. It is suggested then that pearls and horses from the Persian Gulf, together with African ivory and to a lesser extent Arabian incense, all in demand in the Orient, were traded for spices, and in the lower Gulf exchanged for Mesopotamian manufactured goods, such as textiles, pottery, and glass. This theory places considerable importance on the pearling industry in determining the rise of lower Gulf commercial centres. However, conclusive evidence on the role of pearling can only be determined after a study of the period preceding the coming of Islam, and after an investigation of the Southern shore of the Persian Gulf, where at least in the last eight hundred years, the pearling industry has centred.

It will be seen, I hope, from this survey of some of the archaeological results of my work that the sort of information being gained from detailed archaeological research in an historic period can be of great value in giving substance to and augmenting the documentary evidence.